

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Chemically Synthesized Zinc Oxide in Peel-Off Facial Masks: Formulation Strategies, Characterization, and Antimicrobial Potential & Applications

Pratibha Yadav¹, Ranvijay Singh^{*2}, Sanjay Kumar Kushwaha³

¹M. Pharm Scholar Bhavdiya Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Faizabad

²Assistant Professor at Bhavdiya Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Faizabad

³Director, Bhavdiya Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Faizabad

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 19 May. 2026

Keywords:

zinc; zinc oxide; periodontal diseases; periodontitis, Antibacterial activity, Antimicrobial, Feed supplement, Microbial synthesis

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20278179

ABSTRACT

The micro-organism-mediated nanoparticle synthesis is of great importance in the nano-field due to its economic viability, higher and easy bioaccumulation and the process can be scaled up relatively easily. The downstream processing and biomass handling are also facilitated. It is also known to occur naturally. In the current study, the biological synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using *Bacillus nakamurai* sp. (isolated from soil) is reported. The as-synthesized nanoparticles were characterized using X-ray diffraction to confirm AgNP formation. Antibacterial activity of zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO-NPs) has received significant interest worldwide particularly by the implementation of nanotechnology to synthesize particles in the nanometer region. Many microorganisms exist in the range from hundreds of nanometers to tens of micrometers. ZnO-NPs exhibit attractive antibacterial properties due to increased specific surface area as the reduced particle size leading to enhanced particle surface reactivity. ZnO is a bio-safe material that possesses photo-oxidizing and photocatalysis impacts on chemical and biological species. This review covered ZnO-NPs antibacterial activity including testing methods, impact of UV illumination, ZnO particle properties (size, concentration, morphology, and defects), particle surface modification, and minimum inhibitory concentration. Particular emphasis was given to bactericidal and bacteriostatic mechanisms with focus on generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) including hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), OH⁻ (hydroxyl radicals), and O₂⁻² (peroxide). ROS has been a major factor for several mechanisms including cell wall damage due to ZnO-localized interaction, enhanced membrane permeability, internalization of NPs due to loss of proton motive force and uptake of toxic dissolved zinc ions. More than a billion people worldwide suffer from chronic periodontitis.

***Corresponding Author:** Ranvijay Singh

Address: Assistant Professor at Bhavdiya Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Faizabad

Email ✉: anoopkr0555@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

The primary etiological factor of periodontal diseases is dental plaque and the bacteria it contains, particularly *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Tannerella forsythia*, *Treponema denticola*, *Prevotella intermedia*, and *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*. Zinc, owing to its antibacterial properties, can be employed in periodontology. A systematic review protocol of scientific literature was designed following PRISMA recommendations. Data search was conducted in PubMed, Web of Science, and ScienceDirect databases.

INTRODUCTION

Zinc is a metal found in the Earth's crust. It is an irreplaceable and essential element for human health. Approximately 60% of zinc is located in muscles; 30% in bones; and the remaining 10% in skin, hair, pancreas, kidneys, and blood plasma. Intracellularly, it is found in the cytoplasm, vacuoles, organelles, and nucleus. As one of the essential elements and the second most widely distributed chemical element in the human body after iron, it supports the optimal functions of organisms by catalyzing enzyme activity, contributing to the protein structure, and regulating gene expression. Zinc plays a vital role in immune reactions and both cellular and humoral

immunity. [1-2] This trace element is necessary for human health, and its deficiency can lead to various diseases. Zinc is also present in the oral cavity, found in saliva, dental plaque, and enamel hydroxyapatites. Zinc oxide, with its unique physical and chemical properties, such as high chemical stability, high electrochemical coupling coefficient, broad range of radiation absorption and high photostability, is a multifunctional material. [3] The piezo- and pyroelectric properties of ZnO mean that it can be used as a sensor, converter, energy generator and photocatalyst in hydrogen production. Because of its hardness, rigidity and piezoelectric constant it is an important material in the ceramics industry, while its low toxicity, biocompatibility and biodegradability make it a material of interest for biomedicine and in pro-ecological systems. [4] The variety of structures of nanometric zinc oxide means that ZnO can be classified among new materials with potential applications in many fields of nanotechnology. Zinc oxide can occur in one- (1D), two- (2D), and three-dimensional (3D) structures. [5]

Figure 1. Examples of zinc oxide structure

In this review, the methods of synthesis, modification and application of zinc oxide will be

discussed. The zinc oxide occurs in a very rich variety of structures and offers a wide range of

***Corresponding Author:** Ranvijay Singh

Address: Assistant Professor at Bhavdiya Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Faizabad

Email ✉: anoopkr0555@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

properties. [6] The variety of methods for ZnO production, such as vapour deposition, precipitation in water solution, hydrothermal synthesis, the sol-gel process, precipitation from microemulsions and mechanochemical processes, makes it possible to obtain products with particles differing in shape, size and spatial structure. These methods are described in detail in the following sections. In this paper, we have extensively reviewed ideas behind the antibacterial activity of ZnO-NPs covering techniques of evaluating bacteria viability. [7-8] In the subsequent sections, we have discussed the factors affecting the antibacterial activity, including UV illumination, ZnO particle size, concentration, morphology, surface modifications by annealing, surface defects, and the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC). A brief presentation of an experimental case study, carried by authors on antibacterial activity response to *E. coli*, was explored. [9]

1.0. Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles

ZnO is described as a functional, strategic, promising, and versatile inorganic material with a broad range of applications. It is known as II-VI semiconductor, since Zn and O are classified into groups two and six in the periodic table, respectively. ZnO holds a unique optical, chemical sensing, semiconducting, electric conductivity, and piezoelectric properties. It is characterized by a direct wide band gap (3.3 eV) in the near-UV spectrum, a high excitonic binding energy (60 meV) at room temperature [19-23], and a natural n-type electrical conductivity. These characteristics enable ZnO to have remarkable applications in diverse fields. The wide band gap of ZnO has significant effect on its properties, such as the electrical conductivity and optical absorption. [10] The excitonic emission can persevere higher at room temperature and the

conductivity increases when ZnO doped with other metals. Though ZnO shows light covalent character, it has very strong ionic bonding in the Zn-O. Its longer durability, higher selectivity, and heat resistance are preceded than organic and inorganic materials. The synthesis of nano-sized ZnO has led to the investigation of its use as new antibacterial agent. In addition to its unique antibacterial and antifungal properties, ZnO-NPs possess high catalytic and high photochemical activities. ZnO possesses high optical absorption in the UVA (315-400 nm) and UVB (280-315 nm) regions which is beneficial in antibacterial response and used as a UV protector in cosmetics. [11]

• Synthesis of ZnO Nanostructures

The nanostructured ZnO has been emerged as a potential candidate for applications in sensors, energy harvesting, and many electronic devices. Many pronounced applications are being currently explored in the biomedical and antiviral areas. This is as a result of their potential biocompatibility over other metal oxides, solubility in alkaline medium, and the Zn-O terminated polar surfaces. The unique properties and versatility of ZnO pave the way to use various methods to synthesize various ZnO nanostructures. ZnO-NPs can be synthesized through various methods by controlling the synthesis parameters. The properties can be tailored by shape and size, resulting in renewable applications relevant to their structural properties. [12] Mostly, the selected method depends on the desired application, as different methods produce different morphologies and also different sizes of ZnO particles. Accordingly, the chemical and physical parameters such as the solvent type, precursors, pH, and the temperature were highly considered. [13] An assortment of ZnO nanostructures with different growth

morphologies such as nanorods, nanosphere, nanotubes, nanowires, nanoneedles and nanorings have been successfully synthesized. Such unique ZnO nanostructures reflected the richest nanoconfiguration assembly compared to other nano-metal oxides, in terms of properties and structure, such as nanobelts, nanocages, nanocombs and nanosprings/nanohelices. [14] Other shapes can also be obtained, such as ZnO spirals, drums, polyhedrons, disks, flowers, stars, boxes, and plates, those are possibly grown by adjusting the growth conditions. Each nanostructure has specific structural, optical, electrical, and physicochemical properties, permitting remarkable applications. These nanostructures have been fabricated using variety of physical and chemical techniques; however, the chemical techniques allow better control of the particle size and morphology. The most adopted fabrication methods include thermal evaporation of ZnO powders at 1400 C, hydrothermal synthesis, sol gel technique, simple thermal sublimation, self-combustion, polymerized complex method, vapor-liquid-solid technique, double-jet precipitation, and solution synthesis. The solution process was used by several researchers to produce selective ZnO nanostructures. [15] They have synthesized flower-shaped ZnO nanostructures which were produced via solution process at low temperature (90 C) using the zinc acetate dihydrate and NaOH. These nanostructures plus others such as nanowires, nanoplates, and nanorods have been key factors for the antibacterial activity, as each morphology accounts for a certain mechanism of action. Thus, a large number of researchers have been motivated to achieve selective nanostructured ZnO for the antibacterial tests. They succeeded to produce morphologies that were highly compatible with the antibacterial activity. The method yielded structures of spherical surface that showed high antibacterial activity against the tested pathogens. [16]

Similarly, spherical shaped ZnO-NPs in another investigation were obtained via soft chemical solution process, and it was used for the treatment of bacteria (*E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *B. subtilis*, and *S. acidaminiphila*) and cancer cells (HepG2 and MCF-7 cell lines). While have synthesized ZnO powder hydrothermally with the addition of different stabilizing agents leading to different nanostructures. The obtained synthesized ZnO has shown nanorods of hexagonal prismatic and hexagonal pyramid like structures, with some spherical and ellipsoid shapes. These different morphologies displayed pronounced antibacterial effect toward the targeted bacteria. Further discussions of some synthesis methods and their corresponding morphology of ZnO. Usually, antibacterial tests are done in aqueous media or cell culture media. ZnO is known as nearly insoluble in water, it agglomerates immediately with water during synthesis due to the high polarity of water leading to deposition. [17-18] Issues of aggregation, re-precipitation, settling, or non-dissolution impede the synthesis processes. In this regard, a number of researchers considered this difficulty by using certain additives that have no significant effect in the antibacterial activity. As such, in the above-mentioned study [19], the addition of PVA, polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), and poly (a, c, L-glutamic acid) (PGA; see Abbreviations) as stabilizers enhanced ZnO morphology and size for the antibacterial activity. Meanwhile, Zhang et al. have addressed the problem by adding dispersants polyethylene glycol (PEG; see Abbreviations) and PVP (10 % of the amount of ZnO-NPs) which enhanced the stability of ZnO and resulted in ZnO nanofluids, well suited for the antibacterial tests. While other researchers used appropriate capping agents or deflocculants (sodium silicate Na_2SiO_3 or sodium carbonate Na_2CO_3). [20]

- **Crystal Structure of ZnO**

ZnO exhibits three crystalline structures namely, wurtzite, zinc-blende and an occasionally noticed rock-salt. The hexagonal wurtzite structure possesses lattice spacing $a = 0.325$ nm and $c = 0.521$ nm, the ratio $c/a \approx 1.6$ that is very close to the ideal value for hexagonal cell $c/a = 1.633$. Each tetrahedral Zn atom is surrounded by four oxygen atoms and vice versa. The structure is thermodynamically stable in an ambient environment and usually illustrated schematically as a number of alternating planes of Zn and O ions stacked alongside the c -axis. Zinc blende structure is metastable and can be stabilized via growth techniques [21-22].

2.0. Antibacterial Activity of ZnO

Nanoparticles Bacteria are generally characterized by a cell membrane, cell wall, and cytoplasm. The cell wall lies outside the cell membrane and is composed mostly of a homogeneous Rocksalt Membrane Nuclear materials Flagella peptidoglycan layer (which consists of amino acids and sugars). The cell wall maintains the osmotic pressure of the cytoplasm as well the characteristic cell shape. Gram positive bacteria have one cytoplasmic membrane with multilayer of peptidoglycan polymer, and a thicker cell wall (20–80 nm). Whereas gram-negative bacteria wall is composed of two cell membranes, an outer membrane and a plasma membrane with a thin layer of peptidoglycan with a thickness of 7–8 nm.

NPs size within such ranges can readily pass through the peptidoglycan and hence are highly susceptible to damage. [23] The cytoplasm, a jelly-like fluid that fills a cell, involves all the cellular components except the nucleus. The functions of this organelle include growth, metabolism, and replication. [24] Consequently, the cytoplasm contains proteins, carbohydrates, nucleic acids, salts, ions, and water (*80 %). This composition contributes in the electrical conductivity of the cellular structure. The overall charge of bacterial cell walls is negative. Figure 1b shows typical bacteria cell structures. Antibacterial activity is known according to The American Heritage Medical Dictionary 2007, as the action by which bacterial growth is destroyed or inhibited. [25] It is also described as a function of the surface area in contact with the microorganisms. While antibacterial agents are selective concentration drugs capable to damage or inhibit bacterial growth and they are not harmful to the host. These compounds act as chemo-therapeutic agents for the treatment or prevention of bacterial infections. Zinc oxide (ZnO) is a highly promising antimicrobial material with broad-spectrum activity against bacteria, fungi, and viruses. Its antimicrobial action primarily involves reactive oxygen species generation, zinc ion release, membrane disruption, and intracellular toxicity. ZnO nanoparticles exhibit superior activity because of their nanoscale dimensions and increased surface area. [26]

Figure.2: Crystals of ZnO

3.0. Mechanism of Antibacterial Activity of ZnO-NPs

Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO-NPs) exhibit potent antibacterial activity through multiple mechanisms that collectively lead to bacterial cell death. [27] One of the primary mechanisms involves the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$), superoxide anions (O_2^-), and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). These reactive species induce oxidative stress, resulting in lipid peroxidation, protein denaturation, enzyme inactivation, and DNA damage within bacterial cells. [28] Additionally, ZnO-NPs release Zn^{2+} ions, which interfere with cellular metabolic processes and disrupt membrane integrity. Due to their nanoscale size and large surface area, ZnO-NPs can strongly interact with bacterial cell walls through electrostatic attraction, causing membrane permeability changes, leakage of intracellular contents, and eventual cell lysis. Furthermore, nanoparticles may penetrate inside bacterial cells and disturb intracellular organelles and biochemical pathways, ultimately inhibiting bacterial growth and survival. The combined effects of ROS generation, zinc ion release, and membrane disruption make ZnO-NPs highly effective against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. [29]

• UV Illumination Effect

Ultraviolet (UV) illumination significantly enhances the antimicrobial activity of ZnO nanoparticles due to their photocatalytic nature. When ZnO is exposed to UV light, electrons in the valence band become excited and move to the conduction band, leaving behind positively charged holes. These electron-hole pairs react with oxygen and water molecules present on the surface to generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as hydroxyl radicals, superoxide ions, and

hydrogen peroxide. [30-31] These ROS attack microbial cell membranes, proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids, leading to oxidative stress and bacterial cell death. Therefore, ZnO exhibits stronger antibacterial efficiency under UV irradiation compared to dark conditions. [32]

• Impact of ZnO Morphology

The morphology or structural shape of ZnO nanoparticles plays a crucial role in determining their antimicrobial performance. ZnO can be synthesized in various forms such as nanorods, nanowires, nanospheres, nanoflowers, nanotubes, and nanoplates. [33] Different morphologies possess different surface areas, surface defects, and crystal orientations, which influence ROS generation and microbial interaction. Structures with higher surface area, such as nanoflowers and nanorods, provide greater contact with bacterial cells and improved photocatalytic activity, resulting in enhanced antimicrobial effects. Morphology also affects particle penetration into microbial membranes and the release of Zn^{2+} ions. [34-35]

• Surface Modification by Thermal Annealing

Thermal annealing is a heat-treatment process used to improve the structural and surface properties of ZnO nanoparticles. Annealing enhances crystallinity, reduces structural defects, modifies particle size, and improves surface stability. These changes can significantly influence antimicrobial activity. [36-37] Proper annealing temperatures may increase photocatalytic efficiency and ROS production, thereby enhancing bacterial inhibition. Surface modification by thermal annealing also improves particle dispersion and reduces agglomeration, allowing better interaction between ZnO nanoparticles and microbial cells. However,

excessive annealing temperatures may cause particle growth and reduced surface area, which can decrease antimicrobial efficiency. [38]

• **Influence of ZnO Particle Size and Concentration**

Particle size and concentration are among the most important factors affecting the antimicrobial activity of ZnO nanoparticles. Smaller nanoparticles exhibit stronger antibacterial effects because they possess larger surface area-to-volume ratios, higher surface reactivity, and greater ability to penetrate bacterial cell membranes. Nanoparticles with sizes below 50 nm generally show enhanced ROS generation and increased interaction with microorganisms. [39] In addition, antimicrobial activity increases with increasing ZnO concentration because a greater number of particles are available to interact with microbial cells and generate oxidative stress. However, excessively high concentrations may produce cytotoxic effects on normal mammalian cells, making dose optimization essential for biomedical applications [40].

4.0. Mechanisms of microbes mediated synthesis of NPs:

Evidence has shown that enzymes, protein and other compounds produced by microbes play a vital role in the synthesis process. Nonetheless, to date, the data on the identification of chemical components responsible for the synthesis of NPs has been scant. Microbes exhibit the intrinsic potential to synthesise NPs of inorganic materials, which may be routed either by the intracellular or extracellular pathway. [41] Extracellular synthesis is more advantageous and has been widely applied compared to the intracellular route. This is mainly due to the fact that it could be used to synthesise large quantities and involves simple downstream processing that eliminates various steps of

synthesis, easy separation and industrialization. [42] While the recovery process of NPs in the intracellular synthesis requires additional step such as harvesting the cell biomass by centrifugation and subjected to several cycle ultrasonication for cells disruption to obtain the purified NPs. Nonetheless, the specific mechanism with regard to this has not been completely elucidated. [43]

• **Intracellular mechanisms of microbial synthesis**

Evidence has shown that heavy metal ions exhibit great threat to the microbes in which when there is a threat, the microbes will react by grip ping or trapping the ions on the cell wall through the electrostatic interactions [44]. This is due to the fact that metal ion is attracted to the negative charge from the carboxylate groups (specific enzymes, cysteine, polypeptides) that is present on the cell wall. Furthermore, the trapped ions are reduced into the elemental atom initiated by the electron transfer from NADH by NADH-dependent reductase that acts as an electron carrier, which is embedded in the plasma membrane. [45] Finally, the nuclei grow to form NPs and accumulate in the cytoplasm or in the cell wall (periplasmic space). On the other hand, the protein or peptides and amino acids such as cysteine, tyrosine and tryptophan exist inside the cells are responsible for providing stabilization of NPs. Intracellular mechanisms of microbial synthesis In the intracellular synthesis pathway, the cell walls of microbes and ions charge play an important role in the synthesis of NPs. [46] This involves distinctive ion transportation in the microbial cell in the presence of enzymes, coenzymes and others. The cell wall of microbes consists of a variety of polysaccharides and protein, which provides active sites for binding of the metal ions. Moreover, not all microbes are able to synthesise

metal demonstrated the intracellular mechanisms using *Verticillium* sp. for the synthesis of NPs involving three steps, which are trapping, bioreduction and capping. The interaction forces between metal ions and the enzymes present on the cell wall reduce the metal ion within the cell wall leading to the aggregation of metal atoms and formation of metal NPs. The authors also reported the presence of metal NPs on the cytoplasmic membrane by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis, which suggested that the formation of NPs occur in both the cell wall and the cytoplasm of the cell. [47]

- **Extracellular mechanisms of microbial synthesis**

Numerous studies reported that extracellular synthesis is a nitrate reductase-mediated synthesis, which is responsible for the reduction of metal ions into metal NPs. The extracellular synthesis pathway involves enzyme-mediated synthesis which located on the cell membrane or the releasing of the enzyme to the growth medium as an extracellular enzyme. Nitrate reductase is an enzyme in the nitrogen cycle that catalyses the conversion of nitrate to nitrite. For instance, the bioreduction of Zn^{2+} was initiated by the electron transfer from NADH by NADH-dependent reductase that acts as an electron carrier. Consequently, the Zn^{2+} obtained electron and reduced to Zn0.[48] Subsequently, this resulted in the formation of ZnO NPs. Studies have shown that protein produced and secreted by microbes play an important role in the NPs synthesis. Nevertheless, some studies suggested that the native form of the protein is not compulsory for the NPs synthesis process. [49] A study revealed that amino acids present in the protein were found to interact with the Zn^{2+} ions to form NPs. The study also investigated the ability of denatured (heat treated) and native (untreated) protein

present in the fungal cell-free filtrate suspension for the synthesis of ZnO NPs. The results demonstrated that both heat treated and untreated samples were able to synthesize ZnO NPs. Notably, the absorbance spectra result by UV Vis demonstrated a higher reaction rate on the heat treated protein compared to the untreated. This indicates that the synthesis of ZnO NPs was higher in the heat-treated samples. Hence, the results confirmed that the presence of the native form of the protein is not mandatory for the synthesis process. This may attribute to the fact that, the interaction between hydrogen bond and non-polar hydrophobic was disrupted during the heating process. [50] Consequently, this resulted in the exposed contact of amino acids with zinc ions that led to the formation of ZnO NPs. Moreover, the authors also suggested that the biosynthesis of metal NPs was non-enzymatic due to the denaturation of the structure of the enzyme during heat treatment. In some cases, the non-enzymatic mediated synthesis depends on the certain organic functional groups present on the microbial cell wall, which facilitates the reduction of metal ions. The live cell biomass and dead cell (heat killed by autoclaving) of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* were used to synthesize silver NPs. After sonication of the cell, the UV-Vis spectra results demonstrated a strong plasmon resonance between 400 and 450nm for both samples. Both samples were further incubated for a few days. The results indicated that the peak area and height of the UV-Vis spectrum for the dead cell were comparatively higher compared to live cell samples. This indicates a higher productivity of silver NPs. [51]

5.0. Mechanisms of Action of ZnO Nanoparticles Against Bacteria

The antibacterial activity of zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO-NPs) is attributed to several interconnected mechanisms that collectively

inhibit bacterial growth and induce cell death. One of the most widely accepted mechanisms is the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), including hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$), superoxide anions (O_2^-), and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). These reactive molecules cause oxidative stress that damages bacterial proteins, lipids, enzymes, and nucleic acids. [52] Another important mechanism involves the release of Zn^{2+} ions from the nanoparticle surface, which interfere with metabolic pathways, enzyme systems, and membrane transport processes within bacterial cells. ZnO -NPs also interact directly with the bacterial cell membrane through electrostatic attraction, leading to membrane disruption, increased permeability, leakage of intracellular components, and eventual cell lysis. Due to their nanoscale dimensions, the particles may penetrate into bacterial cells and disturb intracellular structures, ribosomes, and DNA replication processes. Additionally, ZnO nanoparticles can inhibit biofilm formation and impair bacterial adhesion, further reducing microbial survival. The synergistic action of ROS generation, zinc ion release, membrane damage, and intracellular interference makes ZnO -NPs effective antimicrobial agents against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. [53]

6.0. Indonesian plants for herbal cosmetics

Some plants in Indonesia have a high potential as a raw material in the manufacture of herbal cosmetics:

1. Jamblang

Jamblang (*Syzygium cumini*), commonly known as Java plum or black plum, is a medicinal plant rich in natural antioxidants such as flavonoids, anthocyanins, tannins, phenolic acids, and vitamin C. The fruit, seeds, leaves, and bark possess strong free radical scavenging activity. Anthocyanins

present in the dark purple fruit help neutralize reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reduce oxidative stress. Jamblang extracts have shown significant antioxidant potential in DPPH, FRAP, and ABTS assays. Due to these properties, the plant is widely investigated for protective effects against diabetes, inflammation, cardiovascular disorders, and aging-related diseases. [54]

2. Tomato

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) is an important dietary source of antioxidants including lycopene, β -carotene, vitamin C, vitamin E, and polyphenols. Lycopene is the major carotenoid responsible for the red color of tomatoes and is considered a highly potent antioxidant capable of quenching singlet oxygen and preventing oxidative cellular damage. Regular consumption of tomatoes is associated with reduced risk of cancer, cardiovascular diseases, and skin aging. Heat processing of tomatoes may increase the bioavailability of lycopene, enhancing antioxidant effectiveness. [55]

3. Dayak onion

Dayak onion (*Eleutherine palmifolia*), also known as red bulb onion, is a traditional medicinal plant widely used in Southeast Asia. It contains bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, phenolics, tannins, and naphthoquinones that contribute to strong antioxidant activity. Extracts of Dayak onion effectively scavenge free radicals and inhibit lipid peroxidation. Studies suggest that its antioxidant properties may help protect against oxidative stress-related disorders including diabetes, hypertension, inflammation, and cancer. The bulb extract is especially valued in herbal medicine because of its high phenolic content. [56]

4. Karsen

Karsen (*Muntingia calabura*), commonly known as Jamaican cherry or Panama berry, possesses significant antioxidant potential due to the presence of flavonoids, phenolic compounds, tannins, and vitamin C. The leaves and fruits exhibit strong free radical scavenging activity and reducing power. Antioxidant compounds in Karsen help minimize oxidative damage to cells and tissues, thereby supporting anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anticancer activities. The plant has gained attention in phytopharmaceutical research for its ability to protect biological systems from oxidative stress-induced damage. [57]

7.0. Skin Care Applications of Medicinal Plants

• Kemuning Leaves

Kemuning leaves (*Murraya paniculata*) are widely used in traditional herbal skincare preparations because of their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. The leaves contain flavonoids, alkaloids, coumarins, and essential oils that help protect the skin from oxidative stress and microbial infections. Kemuning leaf extracts may help reduce acne, soothe skin irritation, improve skin texture, and promote wound healing. Due to their natural antibacterial activity, the leaves are also incorporated into herbal facial cleansers and topical formulations for oily and acne-prone skin. [58]

• Kunyit (Turmeric)

Kunyit or turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) is one of the most important herbal ingredients used in skincare because of its active compound curcumin. Curcumin possesses strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and skin-brightening properties. Turmeric helps reduce acne, pigmentation, redness, and skin inflammation while promoting wound healing and collagen

production. It also protects the skin against oxidative damage caused by UV radiation and environmental pollutants. Turmeric is commonly used in face masks, creams, soaps, and anti-aging cosmetic products. [59]

• Cananga Flowers

Cananga flowers (*Cananga odorata*), commonly known as ylang-ylang flowers, are valued in skincare and aromatherapy because of their soothing, moisturizing, and antimicrobial effects. The flowers contain essential oils rich in linalool, germacrene, and benzyl acetate, which help maintain skin hydration and reduce irritation. Cananga flower extracts and essential oils are frequently used in perfumes, lotions, massage oils, and cosmetic formulations for calming sensitive skin and improving skin softness. Their antimicrobial activity may also assist in controlling minor skin infections and acne-causing microorganisms. [60]

➤ Haircare

Olive oil (*Olea europaea* L.): Olive oil consists of a mixture of triglycerides of oleic acid ester, palmitic acid and other fatty acids, such as squalene (up to 0, 7 %) and sterols (about 0.2% phytosterol and tocopherol). Olive oil acts as hair moisturizer hair and skin irritation reducer. In addition, vitamin E in olive oil protects a hair loss. [61] Thus, olive oil is good to be used in cosmetic hair preparations such as gel and liquid hairtonic. Coconut (*Cocos nucifera*): Coconut is an important member of the Arecaceae (palm) family. Coconut is a large palm, growing up to 30 m, and usually used for cooking. Coconut oil has a good saponification value that can be used as shampoo for hair treatment. Celery (*Apium graveolens*): The main content of celery is butylphthalide known as the main aroma of celery. There are also a number of flavonoids such as graveobiosid A (1-

2%) and B (0, 1 0.7%) as well as fatty acids and phenol group compounds. The main content of fatty acids acid petroselin (40-60%). In addition, the leaves and stems contain steroids as stigmasterol and sitosterol. Celery is also known to have tremendous benefits in hair care because of nutrient contents in celery such as vitamin A, vitamin B, sodium, iron and calcium. Kemiri (*Aleurites moluccanus*): Kemiri seeds are used as a source of oil and spices. It has many mineral deposits such as phosphorus, calcium, potassium, magnesium, and other minerals for stimulating healthy hair, overcoming hair loss and dullness. [62] In Tonga, until now, the mature kemiri (named after "tuitui") is used as a paste, soap and shampoo. Skin whitening Akar manis (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*): Akar manis extract is rich in natural antioxidants. The main antioxidant compound in *Glycyrrhiza glabra* extract is glycyrrhizin (glycyrrhizic acid) and flavonoid. The role of plant extracts on the skin is primarily associated with antioxidant, skin rejuvenation, skin lightening and photoprotection. [63] Previous research showed that a cream formula of plant extracts *Glycyrrhiza glabra* was chemically and physically stable during storage conditions and without induction of allergic or contact dermatitis. Bengkuang (*Pachyrhizus erosus*): Bengkuang has benefits to maintain healthier skin and remove dead skin cells. Bengkuang contains Vitamin C which can nourish the skin and can be used as a base material for the preparation of masks to refresh the face and brighten the skin. Temulawak (*Curcuma xanthorrhiza*): Temulawak is a Zingiberaceae species that is empirically widely used as a traditional medicine especially its rhizome. Anti-acne agents and skin bleaches are an interesting subject on natural skin care of Temulawak because of its vitamin C content. Temulawak is often used as a base ingredient in cosmetic skin lightening preparations in the facial mask, lotion and face cream. [64]

8.0. Effect of various parameters on the optimization process of NPs synthesis

Microbes-mediated synthesis of NPs has the potential to be a great alternative to chemical and physical methods, despite the main drawback in applying biological synthesis of NPs, which refers to the difficulty in controlling both the size and the shape of NPs. [65] The main major concerns in using microbes are to increase yield production for industrial scale, which demand further investigation. It has been widely reckoned that the physicochemical properties of NPs are highly dependent on their size and morphology structures. Studies have proven the direct effects of NPs size and shape on their performance. Sadeghi et al., [66] revealed that the nano plate-shaped NPs exhibited good antibacterial activity due to their large surface area, in comparison to those with nano-rod shape. In another study, ZnO NPs at 12nm effectively inhibited the growth of pathogenic bacteria, when compared to those at 212nm [67]. Therefore, in order to generate effective size distribution, morphologies, and yield production of NPs, it is necessary to optimize both the cultural condition and the varied physical parameters, including pH, temperature, metal ions concentration, microbial age, and reaction time. [68] The biological synthesis of NPs seems to gain better commercial acceptance if the NPs are produced in high yield with the desired size and shape. The schematic representation of parameters for producing the desired NPs [69].

• Effect of pH

Generally, pH is a key factor that has a major role in the synthesis of metal NPs, mainly because pH has the ability to alter the shape of biomolecules that is responsible in capping and stabilizing the NPs [70]. Assessed the biosynthesis of gold NPs using *Verticillium luteoalbum* by varying the pH level to determine its impact on the size and shape

of the generated NPs. The outcomes displayed a majority smaller size of NPs with spherical shape obtained at pH3, in comparison to those retrieved for pH values 7 and 9 that predominantly produced larger NPs with irregular and undefined shapes. [71] Optimization of pH may also be influenced by the species of microbes applied in the synthesis. For instance, an acidophilic bacterium, *Lactobacillus casei*, resulted in increased absorbance of silver NPs production as the pH value was reduced; indicating that growth and enzymes activity of *L. casei* are better in weak acidic environment [72]. In the case of alkaline condition, asserted that hydroxide ion is essential to decrease metal ions. The authors observed rapid increment in silver conversion within less than 30min' reaction time at pH 10; signifying that the protein, which served as a reducing agent, was present in the supernatant and was active in reducing power under alkaline conditions. [73] Additionally, the authors confirmed their results by observing the NPs with TEM analysis that recorded smaller size of NPs ranging between 10 and 15nm. [74]

- **Effect of temperatures**

Numerous researches have investigated the impacts of various temperatures on the size and yield production of NPs. The effects of temperatures on NPs size produced by *Trichoderma viride* at 10°C, 27°C, and 40°C.[75] The UV-Vis spectra outcomes showed that lower wavelength regions at 405 nm were obtained at 40°C and higher wavelength regions at 420nm and 451nm were obtained at 27°C and 10°C, respectively, indicating increment in NPs size at higher wavelength regions.[76] The author also verified their results with TEM analysis that showed a high temperature of 40°C generated smaller monodisperse NPs size ranging between 2 and 4nm, while at a lower temperature, larger NPs

were produced. In another study, maximum production of silver NPs synthesized by *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* was obtained at 80°C with 10–15nm size range. This postulated that higher temperature increased the kinetic energy, thus leading to rapid synthesis rate and maximum NPs with a smaller size [77]. The decrease in particle size with increased temperature is normally due to increment in reaction rate at higher temperature. This causes the metal ion to be consumed rapidly in forming nuclei, while the size is reduced initially due to reduction in the aggregation of the growing NPs. [78]

- **Effect of precursor concentration**

The impact of various precursor salt concentrations on the synthesis of metal NPs using soil fungus *Cladosporium oxysporum* revealed that the optimum concentration of precursor salt at 1.0×10^{-3} mol/L gave maximum NPs yield.[79] Nonetheless, at concentrations 2.0×10^{-3} and 5.0×10^{-3} mol/L, no NPs was generated due to the insufficient biomolecules in minimizing the high amount of metal ions present [80]. This finding is in agreement with that reported absorbance of ZnO NPs by UV-Vis spectra in creased with increment of precursor concentration (2.5×10^{-5} to 1.0×10^{-4} mol/L). They added that further increment in concentration (2.0×10^{-4} mol/L) resulted in broad peak, while decrease in absorbance signified reduction in the synthesis of ZnO NPs.[81] The influence of metal ion concentration on the synthesis of silver NPs using *Penicillium aculeatum* Su1 suggested that high concentration of metal ions increased the aggregation of NPs, which resulted in the formation of larger NPs size. The authors reported that maximum production of NPs yield was obtained at absorbance peak of 415nm by UV vis spectra, whereby as the concentration increased to 2.5×10^{-3} mol/L, the absorbance peak shifted to

435nm; signifying the increased size of NPs formation [82].

CONCLUSION:

Zinc oxide is a multifunctional material because of its many interesting properties (piezo- and pyroelectric), a wide range of UV absorption, and high photostability, biocompatibility and biodegradability. ZnO can also be obtained with a variety of particle structures, which determine its use in new materials and potential applications in a wide range of fields of technology. Therefore the development of a method of synthesizing crystalline zinc oxide which can be used on an industrial scale has become a subject of growing interest in science as well as industry. As can be seen from the survey of recent literature presented here, particles of zinc oxide—both nano- and micrometric—can be produced by many different methods. These can be divided into metallurgical and chemical methods. In metallurgical processes, zinc oxide is obtained by the roasting of a suitable zinc ore, via a direct or indirect process. Chemical methods can be divided into two groups: dispersion methods and condensation methods. In dispersion (mechanochemical) processes, zinc oxide is obtained by the grinding of suitable precursors. The resulting product may contain particles measuring approximately 20 nm. There are many native herbal plants such as dayak onion bulb, kemuning leaf, kecombrang, red betel, kemiri, akarmanis, etc. which can be formulated into various categories of cosmetic preparations such as antioxidants, anti-aging, lip color, liquid bath soap, hair and skin care in accordance with their contents of phytochemicals substances. Thus, cosmetics industry in Indonesia has a great opportunity to become one of the largest herbal cosmetics industries in the world. Technology and knowledge relating to oxide materials of nano- and micrometric dimensions are currently among the

most rapidly developing scientific and technological disciplines. The use of such materials can provide, among other things, more durable ceramics, transparent solar filters blocking infrared and ultraviolet radiation, and catalysts. These materials are also useful in biomedical research and in the diagnosis and treatment of diseases. They can be used to deliver medicines directly to diseased cells, in a way that avoids adverse effects. The survey of the literature that has been given here shows that zinc oxide can be classed as a multifunctional material. This is thanks to such properties as high chemical stability, low electrical constant, high electrochemical coupling index, wide range of radiation absorption, and high photostability. It can be expected that interest in zinc oxide will continue to grow, and that this will lead to the development of new possibilities for its application.

REFERENCES

1. Segets, D.; Gradl, J.; Taylor, R.K.; Vassilev, V.; Peukert, W. Analysis of optical absorbance spectra for the determination of ZnO nanoparticle size distribution, solubility, and surface energy. *ACS Nano* 2009, 3, 1703–1710.
2. Lou, X. Development of ZnO series ceramic semiconductor gas sensors. *J. Sens. Trans. Technol.* 1991, 3, 1–5.
3. Bacaksiz, E.; Parlak, M.; Tomakin, M.; Özcelik, A.; Karakiz, M.; Altunbas, M. The effect of zinc nitrate, zinc acetate and zinc chloride precursors on investigation of structural and optical properties of ZnO thin films. *J. Alloy. Compd.* 2008, 466, 447–450.
4. Wang, J.; Cao, J.; Fang, B.; Lu, P.; Deng, S.; Wang, H. Synthesis and characterization of multipod, flower-like, and shuttle-like ZnO

- frameworks in ionic liquids. *Mater. Lett.* 2005, 59, 1405–1408.
- Wang, Z.L. Splendid one-dimensional nanostructures of zinc oxide: A new nanomaterial family for nanotechnology. *ACS Nano* 2008, 2, 1987–1992.
 - Chaari, M.; Matoussi, A. Electrical conduction and dielectric studies of ZnO pellets. *Phys. B Condens. Matter* 2012, 407, 3441–3447.
 - Özgür, Ü.; Alivov, Y.I.; Liu, C.; Teke, A.; Reshchikov, M.A.; Doğan, S.; Avrutin, V.; Cho, S.J.; Morkoç, H. A comprehensive review of ZnO materials and devices. *J. Appl. Phys.* 2005, 98, doi:10.1063/1.1992666.
 - Bhattacharyya, S.; Gedanken, A. A template-free, sonochemical route to porous ZnO nanodisks. *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 2007, 110, 553–559.
 - Ludi, B.; Niederberger, M. Zinc oxide nanoparticles: Chemical mechanism and classical and non-classical crystallization. *Dalton Trans.* 2013, 42, 12554–12568. 10.
 - Banerjee, D.; Lao, J.Y.; Wang, D.Z.; Huang, J.Y.; Ren, Z.F.; Steeves, D.; Kimball, B.; Sennett, M. Large-quantity free-standing ZnO nanowires. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 2003, 83, 2061–2063.
 - Hahn, Y.B. Zinc oxide nanostructures and their applications. *Korean J. Chem. Eng.* 2011, 28, 1797–1813.
 - Frade, T.; Melo, Jorge, M.E.; Gomes, A. One-dimensional ZnO nanostructured films: Effect of oxide nanoparticles. *Mater. Lett.* 2012, 82, 13–15.
 - Wahab, R.; Ansari, S.G.; Kim, Y.S.; Seo, H.K.; Shin, H.S. Room temperature synthesis of needle-shaped ZnO nanorods via sonochemical method. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 2007, 253, 7622–7626.
 - Kong, X.; Ding, Y.; Yang, R.; Wang, Z.L. Single-crystal nanorings formed by epitaxial self-coiling of polar-nanobelts. *Science* 2004, 303, 1348–1351.
 - Pan, Z.W.; Dai, Z.R.; Wang, Z.L. Nanobelts of semiconducting oxides. *Science* 2001, 291, 1947–1949.
 - Wu, J.J.; Liu, S.C.; Wu, C.T.; Chen, K.H.; Chenm, L.C. Heterostructures of ZnO–Zn coaxial nanocables and ZnO nanotubes. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 2002, 81, 1312–1314.
 - Chen, W.J.; Liu, W.L.; Hsieh, S.H.; Tsai, T.K. Preparation of nanosized ZnO using α brass. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 2007, 253, 6749–6753.
 - Liu, J.; Huang, X.; Duan, J.; Ai, H.; Tu, P. A low-temperature synthesis of multiwhisker-based zinc oxide micron crystals. *Mater. Lett.* 2005, 59, 3710–3714.
 - Huang, Y.; He, J.; Zhang, Y.; Dai, Y.; Gu, Y.; Wang, S.; Zhou, C. Morphology, structures and properties of ZnO nanobelts fabricated by Zn-powder evaporation without catalyst at lower temperature. *J. Mater. Sci.* 2006, 41, 3057–3062.
 - Nikoobakht, B.; Wang, X.; Herzog, A.; Shi, J. Scalable synthesis and device integration of self-registered one-dimensional zinc oxide nanostructures and related materials. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 2013, 42, 342–365.
 - Tien, L.C.; Pearton, S.J.; Norton, D.P.; Ren, F. Synthesis and microstructure of vertically aligned ZnO nanowires grown by high-pressure-assisted pulsed-laser deposition. *J. Mater. Sci.* 2008, 43, 6925–6932.
 - S. Sahoo, Socio-ethical issues and nanotechnology development: perspectives from India, in 2010 10th IEEE Conference on Nanotechnology (IEEE-NANO), Seoul, South Korea, USA, 17–20 August 2010 (IEEE, 2010), pp. 1205–1210. doi:10.1109/NANO.2010.5697887
 - V. Yadav, Nanotechnology, big things from a tiny world: a review. *AIEEE* 3(6), 771–778 (2013)

24. S. Pal, Y.K. Tak, J.M. Song, Does the antibacterial activity of silver nanoparticles depend on the shape of the nanoparticle? A study of the gram-negative bacterium *Escherichia coli*. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 73(6), 1712–1720 (2007). doi:10.1128/AEM.02218-06
25. B. Ashe, A Detail investigation to observe the effect of zinc oxide and Silver nanoparticles in biological system, M.Sc. (Roll NO-607bm004), National Institute of Technology, 2011
26. C. Buzea, I.I. Pacheco, K. Robbie, Nanomaterials and nanoparticles: sources and toxicity. *Biointerphases* 2(4), MR17 MR71 (2007). doi:10.1116/1.2815690
27. J.W. Rasmussen, E. Martinez, P. Louka, D.G. Wingett, Zinc oxide nanoparticles for selective destruction of tumor cells and potential for drug delivery applications. *Expert Opin. Drug Deliv.* 7(9), 1063–1077 (2010). doi:10.1517/17425247.2010.502560
28. Singh RP, Shukla VK, Yadav RS, Sharma PK, Singh PK, Pandey AC. Biological approach of zinc oxide nanoparticles formation and its characterization. *Adv Mater Lett.* 2011; 2:313–7. <https://doi.org/10.5185/amlett.indias.204>.
29. Piccinno F, Gottschalk F, Seeger S, Nowack B. Industrial production quantities and uses of ten engineered nanomaterials in Europe and the world. *JNanopart Res.* 2012;14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11051-012-1109-9>.
30. Sharma D, Sharma S, Kaith BS, Rajput J, Kaur M. Synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles using surfactant free in-air and microwave method. *Appl Surf Sci.* 2011; 257:9661–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2011.06.094>.
31. FDA. FDA (Food and Drug Administration), Washington DC, USA, 2015. Select Committee on GRAS Substances (SCOGS) Opinion: Zinc Salts 2015. <https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/scripts/cdrh/cfdocs/cfcr/CFRSearch.cfm?fr=182.8991>. Accessed 5 Nov 2018.
32. Pulit-Prociak J, Chwastowski J, Kucharski A, Banach M. Functionalization of textiles with silver and zinc oxide nanoparticles. *Appl Surf Sci.* 2016; 385:543–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2016.05.167>.
33. Anbuvaran M, Ramesh M, Viruthagiri G, Shanmugam N, Kannadasan N. Synthesis, characterization and photocatalytic activity of ZnO nanoparticles prepared by biological method. *Spectrochim Acta A Mol Biomol Spectrosc.* 2015; 143:304–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2015.01.124>.
34. Patel P, Kansara K, Senapati VA, Shanker R, Dhawan A, Kumar A. Cell cycle dependent cellular uptake of zinc oxide nanoparticles in human epidermal cells. *Mutagenesis.* 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1093/mutage/gew014>.
35. Sundrarajan M, Ambika S, Bharathi K. Plant-extract mediated synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles using *Pongamia pinnata* and their activity against pathogenic bacteria. *Adv Powder Technol.* 2015; 26:1294–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apt.2015.07.001>.
36. Swain PS, Rao SBN, Rajendran D, Dominic G, Selvaraju S. Nano zinc, an alternative to conventional zinc as animal feed supplement: a review. *Anim Nutr.* 2016; 2:134–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aninu.2016.06.003>.
37. Sturikova H, Krystofova O, Huska D, Adam V. Zinc, zinc nanoparticles and plants. *J Hazard Mater.* 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2018.01.04>.
38. Vallee BL, Falchuk KH. The biochemical basis of zinc physiology. *Physiol Rev.* 1993; 73:79–118. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.1993.73.1.79>.
39. Jamdagni P, Khatri P, Rana JS. Green synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles using flower extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* and

- their antifungal activity. *J King Saud Univ-Sci.* 2018; 30:168–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksus.2016.10.002>.
40. Sirelkhatim A, Mahmud S, Seeni A, Kaus NHM, Ann LC, Bakhori SKM, et al. Review on zinc oxide nanoparticles: antibacterial activity and toxicity mechanism. *Nano-Micro Lett.* 2015; 7:219–42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40820-015-0040-x>.
 41. Moghaddam AB, Moniri M, Azizi S, Rahim RA, Ariff AB, Saad WZ, et al. Biosynthesis of ZnO nanoparticles by a new *Pichia kudriavzevii* yeast strain and evaluation of their antimicrobial and antioxidant activities. *Molecules.* 2017; 22:1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules22060872>.
 42. Saravanan M, Gopinath V, Chaurasia MK, Syed A, Ameen F, Purushothaman N. Green synthesis of anisotropic zinc oxide nanoparticles with antibacterial and cytofriendly properties. *Microb Pathog.* 2018; 115:57–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpath.2017.12.03>.
 43. Jayaseelan C, Rahuman AA, Kirthi AV, Marimuthu S, Santhoshkumar T, Bagavan A, et al. Novel microbial route to synthesize ZnO nanoparticles using *Aeromonas hydrophila* and their activity against pathogenic bacteria and fungi. *Spectrochim Acta A Mol Biomol Spectrosc.* 2012; 90:78–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2012.01.006>.
 44. Ao T, Pierce JL, Pescatore AJ, Cantor AH, Dawson KA, Ford MJ, et al. Effects of feeding different concentration and forms of zinc on the performance and tissue mineral status of broiler chicks. *Br Poult Sci.* 2011; 52:466–71. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071668.2011.588198>.
 45. Sahoo A, Swain R, Mishra SK. Effect of inorganic, organic and nano zinc supplemented diets on bioavailability and immunity status of broilers. *Int J Adv Res.* 2014; 2:828–37.
 46. Gangadoo S, Stanley D, Hughes RJ, Moore RJ, Chapman J. Nanoparticles in feed: Progress and prospects in poultry research. *Trends Food Sci Technol.* 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2016.10.013>.
 47. Khah MM, Ahmadi F, Amanlou H. Influence of dietary different levels of zinc oxide nanoparticles on the yield and quality carcass of broiler chickens during starter stage. *Indian J Anim Sci.* 2015; 85:287–90.
 48. Morales J, Cordero G, Piñeiro C, Durosoy S. Zinc oxide at low supplementation level improves productive performance and health status of piglets. *J Anim Sci.* 2012; 90:436–8. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.53833>.
 49. Wang C, Zhang L, Su W, Ying Z, He J, Zhang L, et al. Zinc oxide nanoparticles as a substitute for zinc oxide or colistin sulfate: effects on growth, serum enzymes, zinc deposition, intestinal morphology and epithelial barrier in weaned piglets. *PLoS One.* 2017;12. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0181136>.
 50. Cho JH, Upadhaya SD, Kim IH. Effects of dietary supplementation of modified zinc oxide on growth performance, nutrient digestibility, blood profiles, fecal microbial shedding and fecal score in weanling pigs. *Anim Sci J.* 2015; 86:617–23. <https://doi.org/10.1111/asj.12329>.
 51. Tsai YH, Mao SY, Li MZ, Huang JT, Lien TF. Effects of nanosize zinc oxide on zinc retention, eggshell quality, immune response and serum parameters of aged laying hens. *Anim Feed Sci Technol.* 2016; 213:99–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anifeedsci.2016.01.009>.
 52. Abedini M, Shariatmadari F, Karimi Torshizi MA, Ahmadi H. Effects of zinc oxide nanoparticles on the egg quality, immune response, zinc retention, and blood parameters of laying hens in the late phase of production. *J Anim Physiol Anim Nutr (Berl).* 2018;

- 102:736–45. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpn.12871>.
53. . Arakha M, Saleem M, Mallick BC, Jha S. The effects of interfacial potential on antimicrobial propensity of ZnO nanoparticle. *Sci Rep.* 2015;5. doi:10.1038/srep09578
 54. Padmavathy N, Vijayaraghavan R. Enhanced bioactivity of ZnO nano particles—an antimicrobial study. *Sci Technol Adv Mater.* 2016; 9:035004.
 55. Derewacz DK, Goodwin CR, McNeesCR, McLeanJA, Bachmann BO. Antimicrobial drug resistance affects broad changes in metabolomic phenotype in addition to secondary metabolism. *Proc Natl Acad Sci.* 2013;110(6):2336–2341. doi:10.1073/pnas.1218524110
 56. Wintersdorff CJH, Penders J, van Niekerk JM, et al. Dissemination of antimicrobial resistance in microbial ecosystems through horizontal gene transfer. *Front Microbiol.* 2016;7. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2016.00173
 57. Carrillo-Munoz AJ, Giusiano G, Ezkurra PA, Quindós G. Antifungal agents: mode of action in yeast cells. *Rev Esp Quimioter.* 2006;19 (2):130–139.
 58. Landini P, Antoniani D, Burgess JG, Nijland R. Molecular mechanisms of compounds affecting bacterial biofilm formation and dispersal. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* 2010;86(3):813–823. doi:10.1007/s00253-010-2468-8
 59. Hooper DC. Mechanisms of action of antimicrobials: focus on fluoroquinolones. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2001;32(Supplement 1): S9–S15. doi:10.1086/319370
 60. Wang L, Hu C, Shao L. The antimicrobial activity of nanoparticles: present situation and prospects for the future. *Int J Nanomedicine.* 2017; 12:1227. doi:10.2147/IJN.S121956
 61. Rai M. Nanobiotecnologia verde: biossínteses de nanopartículas metálicas e suas aplicações como nanoantimicrobianos. *Ciência E Cultura.* 2013;65 (3):44–48. doi:10.21800/S0009-67252013000300014
 62. 10. Durairaj B, Muthu S, Xavier T. Antimicrobial activity of *Aspergillus niger* synthesized titanium dioxide nanoparticles. *Adv Appl Sci Res.* 2015; 6:45–48.
 63. Firouzabadi FB, Noori M, Edalatpanah Y, Mirhosseini M. ZnO nanoparticle suspensions containing citric acid as antimicrobial to control *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus cereus* in mango juice. *Food Control.* 2014; 42:310–314. doi: 10.1016/j.foodcont.2014.02.012
 64. Raghupathi KR, Koodali RT, Manna AC. Size-dependent bacterial growth inhibition and mechanism of antibacterial activity of zinc oxide nanoparticles. *Langmuir.* 2011;27(7):4020–4028. doi:10.1021/la104825u
 65. Manoharan C, Pavithra G, Dhanapandian S, Dhamodaran P, Shanthi B. Properties of spray pyrolysed ZnO: Sn thin films and their antibacterial activity. *Spectrochim Acta Part A.* 2015; 141:292–299. doi: 10.1016/j.saa.2015.01.051
 66. LiuY, HeL, MustaphaA, LiH, HuZQ, LinM. Antibacterial activities of zinc oxide nanoparticles against *Escherichia coli* O157:H7. *J Appl Microbiol.* 2009;107(4):1193–1201. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2672.2009.04303.x
 67. Janaki AC, Sailatha E, Gunasekaran S. Synthesis, characteristics and antimicrobial activity of ZnO nanoparticles. *Spectrochim Acta Part A.* 2015; 144:17–22. doi: 10.1016/j.saa.2015.02.041
 68. Pasquet J, Chevalier Y, Couval E, Bouvier D, Bolzinger M-A. Zinc oxide as a new antimicrobial preservative of topical products: interactions with common formulation

- ingredients. *Int J Pharm.* 2015;479(1):88–95. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpharm.2014.12.031
69. Sirelkhatim A, Mahmud S, Seeni A, et al. Review on zinc oxide nanoparticles: antibacterial activity and toxicity mechanism. *Nano Micro Lett.* 2015;7(3):219–242. doi:10.1007/s40820-015-0040-x
70. Zheng MJ, Zhang LD, Li GH, Shen WZ. Fabrication and optical properties of large-scale uniform zinc oxide nanowire arrays by one-step electrochemical deposition technique. *Chem Phys Lett.* 2002;363(1):123–128. doi:10.1016/S0009-2614(02)01106-5
71. Jagadish C, Pearton SJ. *Zinc Oxide Bulk, Thin Films and Nanostructures: Processing, Properties, and Applications.* Elsevier; 2011.
72. Seven O, Dindar B, Aydemir S, Metin D, Ozinel MA, Icli S. Solar photocatalytic disinfection of a group of bacteria and fungi aqueous suspensions with TiO₂, ZnO and Sahara Desert dust. *J Photochem Photobiol A.* 2004;165(1):103–107. doi: 10.1016/j.jphotochem. 2004.03.005
73. Adams LK, Lyon DY, Alvarez PJJ. Comparative eco-toxicity of nanoscale TiO₂, SiO₂, and ZnO water suspensions. *Water Res.* 2006;40(19):3527–3532. doi: 10.1016/j.watres.2006.08.004
74. Hirota K, Sugimoto M, Kato M, Tsukagoshi K, Tanigawa T, Sugimoto H. Preparation of zinc oxide ceramics with a sustainable antibacterial activity under dark conditions. *Ceram Int.* 2010;36 (2):497–506. doi: 10.1016/j.ceramint.2009.09.026
75. d'Água RB, Branquinho R, Duarte MP, et al. Efficient coverage of ZnO nanoparticles on cotton fibres for antibacterial finishing using a rapid and low cost in situ synthesis. *New J Chem.* 2018;42 (2):1052–1060. doi:10.1039/C7NJ03418K
76. Kadiyala U, Turali-Emre ES, Bahng JH, Kotov NA, VanEpps JS. Unexpected insights into antibacterial activity of zinc oxide nanoparticles against methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). *Nanoscale.* 2018;10(10):4927–4939. doi:10.1039/c7nr08499d
77. Cho W-S, Duffin R, Howie SEM, et al. Progressive severe lung injury by zinc oxide nanoparticles; the role of Zn²⁺ dissolution inside lysosomes. *Part Fibre Toxicol.* 2011;8(1):27. doi:10.1186/1743-8977-8-27
78. Li Y, Zhang W, Niu J, Chen Y. Mechanism of photogenerated reactive oxygen species and correlation with the antibacterial properties of engineered metal-oxide nanoparticles. *ACS Nano.* 2012;6 (6):5164–5173. doi:10.1021/nn300934k
79. Lallo da Silva B, Caetano BL, Chiari-Andréo BG, Pietro RCLR, Chiavacci LA. Increased antibacterial activity of ZnO nanoparticles: influence of size and surface modification. *Colloids Surf B.* 2019; 177:440–447. doi: 10.1016/j.colsurfb.2019.02.013
80. Heinlaan M, Ivask A, Blinova I, Dubourguier H-C, Kahru A. Toxicity of nanosized and bulk ZnO, CuO and TiO₂ to bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* and crustaceans *Daphnia magna* and *Thamnocephalus platyurus*. *Chemosphere.* 2008;71(7):1308–1316. doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere. 2007.11.047
81. He L, Liu Y, Mustapha A, Lin M. Antifungal activity of zinc oxide nanoparticles against *Botrytis cinerea* and *Penicillium expansum*. *Microbiol Res.* 2011;166(3):207–215. doi: 10.1016/j.micres.2010.03. 003
82. Lipovsky A, Nitzan Y, Gedanken A, Lubart R. Antifungal activity of ZnO nanoparticles—the role of ROS mediated cell injury. *Nanotechnology.* 2011;22(10):105101. doi:10.1088/0957-4484/22/10/105101.

HOW TO CITE: Pratibha Yadav, Ranvijay Singh*, Sanjay Kumar Kushwaha Chemically Synthesized Zinc Oxide in Peel-Off Facial Masks: Formulation Strategies, Characterization, and Antimicrobial Potential & Applications, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2026, Vol 4, Issue 5, 4622-4639. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20278179>

